

Using in silico design methods to create *de novo* proteins that selectively modulate apoptosis

Richard Birkinshaw

Webinar: Leveraging deep learning to design custom protein-binding proteins

16 September 2025

Talk Outline

1. Selectively targeting BAK with *de novo* proteins
2. Using RFDiffusion to modulate designed protein function

Apoptosis overview

Bandyopadhyay A, *et al.* PLoS Genet 2006, 2(12): e216.

- Development
- Host Defense
- Cancer prevention

BCL2 family proteins - BAK

Human BCL2 family proteins

Pro-apoptotic

BID (+ many unstructured BH3-only proteins)

Pro-survival

BCL2, BCLx1, BCLw, MCL1, BFL1, BCLb

Pro-apoptotic effector

BAK, BAX (+ BOK)

BAK

- BAK unfolds on the mitochondrial outer membrane
- BAK dimerises
- Dimers oligomerise to form pores
- Cytochrome *c* is released
- Triggers caspase cascade

Part 1 – Binding BAK and BAX with synthetic proteins

eLife

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CANCER BIOLOGY, COMPUTATIONAL AND SYSTEMS BIOLOGY

Computationally designed high specificity inhibitors delineate the roles of BCL2 family proteins in cancer

[f](#) [t](#) [e](#) [r](#)

Stephanie Berger¹, Erik Procko, Daciana Margineantu, Erinna F Lee, Betty W Shen, Alex Zelter, Daniel-Adriano Silva, Kusum Chawla, Marco J Herold [see all](#) »

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- Collaboration with Stephanie Berger (Baker Lab)
- Three helix bundle (BINDI), binds BHRF1 – high thermostability (mutation tolerant)
- Design proteins to target BAK (and BAX)

in silico design BAK and BAX binders

- Align BHRF1-Bindi structure on BAK structure.
- Mutate BH3 helix residues to Ala – except h1-3 positions and GD.
- Rosetta MotifGraft samples mutations to the BH3
- Graft back into BINDI and BINDI:BAK and score
- End with Computationally Designed Protein (CDP02)

CDP02 is a high affinity BAK binder

		Pro-apoptotic		Pro-survival						
		Bak	Bax	Bcl-2	Bcl-xL					
native ligands	Bim-BH3	4,000 ± 2,000	500 ± 100	0.9 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.1					
	Bid-BH3	> 4 μM	464 ± 4	47 ± 5	2.3 ± 0.4					
		Pro-apoptotic		Pro-survival						
		Bak	Bax	Bcl-2	Bcl-xL	Bcl-w	Mcl-1	Bfl-1	Bcl-B	NA
Bak comp. des.		60 ± 20	1,200 ± 800	130 ± 30	30,000 ± 20,000	800 ± 100	5.4 ± 0.3	10 ± 10	200 ± 100	NA

- CDP affinities ~ 60 nM for BAK
- Unfortunately binds pro-survivals too – not selective

Selectivity and affinity maturation of BAK binders

- Perform SSM on CDPs
- Select for BAK enrichment vs Pro-survival
- 2 rounds giving: α BAK then α BAX2

α BAK2 is a high affinity, selective BAK binder

α BAK: 400 pM, >300-fold selectivity

		Pro-apoptotic		Pro-survival	
		Bak	Bax	Bcl-2	Bcl-xL
native ligands	Bim-BH3	4,000 \pm 2,000	500 \pm 100	0.9 \pm 0.2	1.6 \pm 0.1
	Bid-BH3	> 4 μ M	464 \pm 4	47 \pm 5	2.3 \pm 0.4

		Pro-apoptotic		Pro-survival						
		Bak	Bax	Bcl-2	Bcl-xL	Bcl-w	Mcl-1	Bfl-1	Bcl-B	
designed/evolved	Bak comp. des.	60 \pm 20	1,200 \pm 800	130 \pm 30	30,000 \pm 20,000	800 \pm 100	5.4 \pm 0.3	10 \pm 10	200 \pm 100	NA
	Bak evolved variant rd1	7 \pm 2	10,000 \pm 10,000	40 \pm 2	100,000 \pm 200,000	9,550 \pm 60	500 \pm 200	1,700 \pm 800	12,000 \pm 8,000	6
	α BAK	0.4 \pm 0.2	> 9 μ M	133 \pm 8	5,700 \pm 100	5,000 \pm 5,000	310 \pm 30	960 \pm 80	3,000 \pm 1,000	333

BAK:αBAK2 complex crystallography

- Heterodimers of BAK and αBAK2
- BAK is unlatched
- Design model very close to experimental structure, despite BAK conformation change
- Validates computational design and BAK binding
- What are the functional consequences of unlatching?

Liposome assays

Mitochondrial lipid mix liposome

cBid →

BAK permeabilizes the liposomes

- Liposomes loaded with self quenching fluorescent dye
- Rupture of liposomes allows dye release and increases fluorescence
- Tool to monitor BAK activation

Liposome assays

No activating stimulus

With activating stimulus

- In absence of cBID α BAK2 activates **BAK** when sub-stoichiometric, but inhibits when in α BAK2 is in excess
- Same trend observed in presence of cBID
- Functions as an inhibitor and an activator – concentration dependent

Summary Part 1

Selectively targeting BAK with *de novo* proteins

- Computational modelling can design BAK binders
- SSM key to improving affinity and selectivity of binders
- Binders bind as predicted in the BH3 binding groove
- Structures reveal unexpected conformational change upon binding
- *in vitro* experiments reveal unexpected dual function to binder
- Binder concentration is key – low concentrations activate, high concentrations inhibit

Part 2

Using RFDiffusion to modulate designed protein function

Article | Published: 01 December 2021

De novo protein design by deep network hallucination

[Ivan Anishchenko](#), [Samuel J. Pellock](#), [Tamuka M. Chidyausiku](#), [Theresa A. Ramelot](#), [Sergey Ovchinnikov](#), [Jingzhou Hao](#), [Khushboo Bafna](#), [Christoffer Norn](#), [Alex Kang](#), [Asim K. Bera](#), [Frank DiMaio](#), [Lauren Carter](#), [Cameron M. Chow](#), [Gaetano T. Montelione](#) & [David Baker](#)

[Nature](#) **600**, 547–552 (2021) | [Cite this article](#)

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Marjan Hadian-Jazi (Monash – Knott lab)

RESEARCH ARTICLE | PROTEIN DESIGN

Scaffolding protein functional sites using deep learning

[JUE WANG](#), [SIDNEY LISANZA](#), [DAVID JUERGENS](#), [DOUG TISCHER](#), [JOSEPH L. WATSON](#), [KARLA M. CASTRO](#), [ROBERT RAGOTTE](#), [AMIJAI SARAGOVI](#), [LUKAS F. MILLES](#), [...], AND [DAVID BAKER](#) +14 authors [Authors Info & Affiliations](#)

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Eve Mahlab Award Blue Sky Research

- Inspired by Hallucination and Inpainting papers
- Establish workflow at WEHI
- Can we build new functionality into α BAK2?
- Pilot study to assess capabilities

RFDiffusion

Article

De novo design of protein structure and function with RFDiffusion

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06415-8>

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Motif scaffolding

- Denoising diffusion probabilistic models (DDPMs)
- Introduce noise into protein structures and learn to denoise
- During denoising can guide towards desired target

Install new domain into α BAK2

Current binder

New binder

- Can we use RFDiffusion to motif scaffold new functionality into α BAK2?
- Block BAK binding by installing small molecule binding site into α BAK2
- Three objectives:
 1. Retain BAK binding
 2. Install rapamycin binding
 3. Modulate BAK binding with Rapamycin

Concept

- Use established FKBP-FRB rapamycin induced dimerisation
- Merge into α BAK2 structure

RFDiffusion

- Run standard workflow
- But run in discrete steps – not standard pipeline
- Full AF2 at end
 - Binder +/- BAK target

RFdiffusion

- RFdiffusion command

```
run_inference.py \  
inference.output_prefix=Rfdiffusion \  
inference.input_pdb=design_model.pdb \  
'contigmap.contigs=[A1-41/5-12/A49-115/10-50/A146-164/2/A167-192/5-15/A203-220/15-45/A251-272/4-9/A278- \  
294]' \  
inference.num_designs=2000
```


Design selection

- Request 6000 designs from RFdiffusion
 - Reject ~5870 due to clashes at Rapamycin or BAK binding site
 - Run Protein MPNN and AF2 – reject 90
 - Manually inspect the remaining
 - Shortlist to 11 (4 mini binders)
-
- Expression trials in *E. coli*
 - Batch culture 1L and purify
-
- Check binding to BAK and Rapamycin by SPR 🙌
 - Check function in liposome assays 🙌

BAK and Rapamycin Dual binders

BAK mini binders

Design selection – expression trials

- All expressed in *E. coli* BL21 – small scale (6 mL)
- Select top expressers for large scale expression – 1 L

Design selection – purification

- Expressed 6 dual binders at scale
- Expressed 2 mini binders at scale
- Good yields for 7 of 8 tested
 - Move to further characterisation
- Various degrees of success – no 🦄

Design selection – BAK binding SPR

Dual binders

3 with reasonable fits

2 odd curves – sticky?

Mini binders

- Range of affinities for BAK 1 nM – 10 μM
- Range of on and off rates

Design selection – BAK activity

Dual binders

Mini binders

- All activate BAK
- Minibinder potency correlates with SPR affinity

Design selection – Rapamycin binding

SPR

Liposome

- SPR shows binding
- Modest change (4-fold) in BAK activity

- SPR shows no binding
- No change in BAK activity

Summary – Part 2

Using RFDiffusion to modulate designed protein function

- Established a RFDiffusion workflow at WEHI
 - Integrated into Nextflow and Seqera by Julie Iskander
- RFD 6000 Dual binders, rejection prior to MPNN gives 130, after AF2 40 designs, final selection 11
- RFD 30 mini binders, final selection 4
- Expression trials showed all 15 expressed in *E. coli* – various levels
- Further characterisation of 8 top expressers showed problems at size exclusion for Dual binders
 - Degradation products, oligomerization. Requires optimisation
- 5 confirmed BAK binders
 - 3 Dual and 2 Mini binders, 1 nM to 10 μ M
- 4 confirmed to activate BAK
 - 2 Dual and 2 Mini binders
- 1 confirmed Rapamycin binder - 250 nM
- Modulation of BAK binding inconclusive at this stage
- Methods outdated

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WEHI

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Marjan Hadian-Jazi

ONJ
Erinna Lee
Doug Fairlie

Baker Lab
Stephanie Berger
David Baker

Eve Mahlab Awards
for Blue Sky Research

Summary

Part 1: Targeting BAK and BAX with de novo proteins

- Computational modelling can design BAK binders
- SSM key to improving affinity and selectivity of binders
- Binders bind as predicted in the BH3 binding groove
- Structures reveal unexpected conformational change upon binding,
- *in vitro* experiments reveal unexpected dual function to BAK binder

Part 2 - Using RFDiffusion to in-paint new function into designed proteins

- Established a pipeline to de novo design new proteins with RFDiffusion
- From 6000 requested Dual binder models able to shortlist to 11 based on various criteria
- Rapamycin and BAK binding achieved
- Methods now improved

Model for α BAK2 function

Preferred fonts

Arial Bold
Arial Regular

Primary WEHI colour palette

Yellow
c10 m0 y81 k0
r237 g233 b83
HEX #ece953

Green
c70 m0 y100 k9
r73 g169 b66
HEX #49a942

Blue
c85 m53 y0 k0
r35 g114 b185
HEX #2372b9

Green
c0c m0 y0 k80
r88 g89 b91
HEX #58595b

Secondary WEHI colour palette

Orange
c0 m67 y100 k0
r244 g117 b33
HEX #f37520

Red
c0 m100 y67 k5
r255 g21 b70
HEX #e01545

Purple
c60 m85 y0 k0
r126 g73 b157
HEX #7d489c

Light Blue
c75 m0 y5 k0
r0 g188 b231
HEX #00bce7

Teal
c100 m0 y48 k0
r0 g169 b160
HEX #00a99f

The colour palette is loaded into this template

> More Fill Colours...

